

studies were than carried out using equimolar solutions ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) of $\text{Fe}(5\text{MeOAS})^{+2}$ and Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate. The absorbances were measured at the λ_{max} (600 nm) of the $\text{Fe}(5\text{MeOAS})^{+2}$. Two sets of solutions, one with and the other without Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate were prepared. The difference in the absorbance of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function in the Job's curve. The maximum de-colourization was observed at a ratio of iron(III) : Na_2EDTA /ammonium oxalate = 1 : 1. This indicates the formation of a complex corresponding to the formula $\text{FeEDTA}^-/\text{Fe C}_2\text{O}_4^{+}$ under the experimental conditions used.

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On the use of Methyl Alcohol as a Solvent for Bromine in Kinetic Studies

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RECENTLY^{1,2,3}, the kinetics and mechanism of the addition of bromine to compounds containing an ethylenic double bond have been investigated, using anhydrous and aqueous acetic acids as solvents. However, our attempts to make similar kinetic investigations using methyl alcohol as solvent were not quite successful since solutions of bromine in methyl alcohol are unstable due to the formation of methyl hypobromite. Recently Seth and Bose⁴ have studied the kinetics of the bromination of cinnamic acid and its derivatives in methyl alcohol as solvent. In the present paper, we are therefore reporting our findings regarding the stability of bromine in methyl alcohol.

It has been observed^{5,6} that, in a solution of bromine in methyl alcohol, methyl hypobromite is formed according to the equilibrium

When an ethylenic compound reacts with bromine in methyl alcohol, two products, are formed *viz.*, the dibromide and the methoxy bromide, although different proposals have been made regarding the mechanism of formation of these products^{6,7}. In fact Bartlett and Trabell⁷ found that, in the reaction between stilbene and bromine in methyl alcohol, the fraction of methoxy bromide in the products was about 83% in the presence of 0.2M sodium bromide and 99% in the absence of added bromide. The above observations by Bartlett and Tarbell⁷ and by Meinel⁶ are consistent with our findings (see experimental section below) which clearly show that a solution of bromine in methyl alcohol is unstable. The assumption of Seth and Bose⁴ that, in the bromination of cinnamic acid (and its derivatives) in methyl alcohol, the only product is dibromo-cinnamic acid is therefore not valid.

Experimental

A standard solution of bromine in acetic acid was prepared. 5 ml of the bromine solution was added to a known but fixed amount of methyl alcohol taken in a groundglass-stoppered tube (capacity 20 ml) which was also provided with a cup at its mouth, similar to that in an iodine-flask. After allowing the bromine to react with the methyl alcohol for a known duration of time in a thermostat at 30°, potassium iodide solution (10%) was added and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate (0.01N). It is to be noted that, in this method, the loss of bromine due to volatility⁸ is less than 1%. Further details of the experimental technique and the purification of the acetic acid are given in earlier papers from this laboratory^{8,9}.

Results are given in Table 1. The first eight entries are for B.D.H. Analar methyl alcohol, using 10 ml of the alcohol in each case. The remaining entries are for methyl alcohol (20 ml in each case) obtained by purifying a commercial sample by

TABLE 1--RESULTS SHOWING THE INSTABILITY OF BROMINE IN METHYL ALCOHOL

Duration for which Br_2 was allowed to react with methyl alcohol min.	Decrease in $[\text{Br}_2]$ %
0	—
10	4.5
25	10.0
43	16.0
60	22.0
79	26.5
97	31.5
119	36.0
0	—
30	23.7
100	54.2
130	62.6
310	75.3

successive treatment with quick-lime, potassium hydroxide pellets, magnesium and iodine and refluxing and distilling at each stage, as described in detail by Fieser¹⁰. The results clearly show that the concentration of bromine decreases with time, indicating reaction between bromine and methyl alcohol.

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4-Thiazolidinones. Part X

Syntheses of 3-(β -Aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-Alkoxyphenyl)-Imino-4-Thiazolidinones and 3-Benzyl-2-(2-Pyridyl)-2-Thiazolyl-2/3-pyridylmethyl)-Imino-4-Thiazolidinones.

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IN continuation of our work on 4-thiazolidinones 3-(β -aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-alkoxyphenyl) imino-4-thiazolidinones and 2-benzyl-2-(2-pyridyl)/2-thiazolyl/2/3-pyridyl methyl imino-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared by condensation of monochloroacetic acid with:

- (i) 1-(β -aryloxyethyl)-3-(4-alkoxyphenyl)-2-thioureas;
- (ii) 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thioureas;
- (iii) 1-benzyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)-2-thioureas;
- (iv) 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridylmethyl)-2-thioureas; and
- (v) 1-benzyl-3-(3-pyridylmethyl)-2-thioureas.

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TABLE I. 3-(β -ARYLOXYETHYL)-3-(4-ALKOXYPHENYL)-2-THIOUREAS

No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	C ₂ H ₅	113	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.2	10.1
2.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	134	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.2
3.	4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	168	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.2
4.	2-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	131	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.6	9.7
5.	4-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	145-46	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.7	9.7
6.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	113	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.3	9.3
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	121	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.4	9.3
8.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	131	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.3	8.3
9.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	121	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.9	8.7
10.	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	112	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.3
11.	2-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	86-87	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.4	8.5
12.	4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	136	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.7	8.5
13.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	83	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.6	8.9
14.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	118	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.0	8.9
15.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	99	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.5	8.6
16.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	135	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.4	8.6
17.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	111	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.7	7.8
18.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	175	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.1	8.2
19.	H	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	98	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.8	8.9
20.	2-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	93	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.1	8.2
21.	4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	137	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.0	8.2
22.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	87-88	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.7	8.6
23.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	114-15	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.8	8.6
24.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	70	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.0	8.3
25.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	105-06	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.2	8.3
26.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	106	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.4	7.5
27.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	166	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.8	7.9